

ACETAMIPRID RESIDUES IN PEPPER AFTER APHIDES CONTROL IN GREENHOUSES

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SUMMARY: The subject of this study was determination of acetamiprid residues in pepper. The insecticide was used for the control of potato aphides (Macrosiphum euphorbiae, Thomas 1878), in a plastic greenhouse in the district of Durres in 2011. The experiment was laid out with two doses of 20 and 30 g a.i./ha of acetamiprid. The treatments were carried out with minimum and maximum doses recommended. Acetamiprid was found to be effective against aphides in pepper. The samples were taken on the first, third, fifth and seventh day after the last treatment. The Pre Harvest Interval (PHI) of acetamiprid is seven days. On the expiry of PHI the residue level of acetamiprid was lower than Maximum Residue Level (MRL) values. It should be emphasized that the results of the analysis point at the fact that PHI must be observed so as to avoid the increased levels of acetamiprid in fruits of pepper.

Key words: pepper, *Macrosiphum euphorbiae*, acetamiprid, residue, PHI, MRL.

INTRODUCTION

Aphides are an important pest in sweet pepper protected crops (Valério, 2003, 2004, 2005). Hemiptera: Aphididae are very destructive and often dominant pests in sweet pepper greenhouses (Ramakers, 2004). They produce large amounts of honeydew which cause damage on plants and the crop production may be reduced. In sweet pepper protected crops some aphid species can cause direct and indirect damage.

With so many aphid species that can cause damage to sweet pepper there is tradi-

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tional chemical control, that is costly for farmers and has many disadvantages either for public health or for the environment, particularly for its negative effects on beneficial organisms (Zhang, 2000; Ostman, 2001; Barrenechea, et al, 2004). Recently, insecticide neonicotinoids have been the fastest growing classes of insecticides in modern crop protection with wide spectrum effect against sucking and certain chewing insect pests (Jeschke and Naumen, 2008). Changes of aphid sensitivity to the insecticides from the group of neonicotinoids have been referred to in literature of cross resistance of the species *Bemisia tabaci* (Homoptera: Aleurodidae) to thiamethoxam and acetamiprid (Elbert and Nauen, 2000), but in the region of the Central and Southeast Europe, a change in the efficacy of products from these insecticides have not been registered, therefore those insecticides are still successfully used (Indić et al., 2009). These chemical insecticides act agonistically on insect Nicotinic Acetylcholine Receptors (nAChR), blocking the nicotinic neural pathway causing the accumulation of neurotransmitter acetylcholine (Matsuda et al., 2001; Lazić et al., 2008; Tomizawa and Cassida, 2009). Their chemical structure resembles the nicotine structure to a great extent, hence the name neonicotinoid (Bursić et al., 2010). They are especially active on Homopteran pest species (Naumen *et al.*, 2003).

Because of a realistic risk of the development of resistance to compounds from the group of neonicotinoids, it is recommended for the control of aphides and other harmful insects to avoid alternative application of compounds based on thiamethoxam, acetamiprid, imidacloprid and thiacloprid (Vuković, 2006).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Monitoring aphid species. A greenhouse with sweet pepper was sampled weekly. When the conditions were favorable to the development of aphid populations, the frequency of sampling was intensified. Greenhouses were divided into ten sections and one sweet pepper plant of each section was sampled for monitoring aphid species.

Leaves were randomly collected from two of the three plant levels (superior, medium and inferior). The treatments were carried out with chlorpyrifos, deltamethrin and acetamiprid. Acetamiprid (Mospilan SP 20), Chemical subclass: Chloronicotinyl, International Union for Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) name: *E-N1-[6-chloro-3-pyridyl)methyl]-N2-cyano-N1-methylacetamide*. It was used at the rate of 20 g a.i./ha and 30 g a.i./ha on 15.06.2011. and the samples were taken on the first, third and seventh day after the treatment.

The greenhouse where we conducted the experiments with a surface 1100 m², was planted with hybrid pepper. The experiment to assess the level of acetamiprid waste was applied under this scheme: Treatments: 1. Acetamiprid dose 20 g a.i./ha (10 plants), 2. Acetamiprid dose 30 g a.i./ha. (10 plants), 3. Control without treatment (10 plants).

The aphid diagnosis (Photo 1) was made in the Plant Protection Laboratory. The Photo 2a and 2b, show the male and female of *Macrosiphum euphorbiae*.

Photo 1. Moment of sampling for the diagnosis of aphid.

Photo 2. Male (a) and female (b); *Macrosiphum euphorbiae*

In each treatment, 45 leaves of the same physiological age were sampled. The leaves were all sampled from the height of about 1 m above the ground, from 45 different plants at the treatment patch. On each leaf all aphides were counted over the entire leaf surface. At the beginning of this study (zero count) the level of the aphids population was very high which caused an immense damage to the pepper plants.

Gas Chromatography system. Gas Chromatograph with programmed temperature, with electron capture detector (ECD), capillary column and split less injectors. Capillary column of molten silicon, DB-5, with 0,32 mm internal diameter, length 30 m, film thickness of 0,25 μm . Helium carrier gas flow rate: 1 mL/min. Oven temperature program: 170°C for 1 min, rising to 10°C/min up to 250°C, which is held 7 min. Injector temperature: 250°C, the time of closing of Split: 1 min. Detector temperature: 350°C. Make-up gas for ECD: nitrogen with 30 mL/min. System calibrated or the calibration curve verified each day. In these conditions, the time ratio of acetamiprid is 7.297 min.

RESULTS

The obtained parameters of the validation of acetamiprid determination by gas chromatography with electron capture detector (GC-ECD) are shown in graphs as well as in figures 3 and 4.

Calibration:

$Y = aX + b$; $a = 2.038266\text{e-}006$; $b = -8.793676\text{e-}003$; $R^2 = 0.9988559$; $R = 0.9994278$.
Mean RF: 1.917529e-006; RF SD: 1.760782e-007; RF %RSD : 9.182557.

Figure 1. Calibration curve for standard of acetamidrid

Figure 2. Chromatogram of acetamidrid standard

During the assays, one aphid species was identified *M. euphorbiae*. The occurrence of this population dynamic of the aphid species, much different from the other years, took place when problems in development of sweet pepper plants occurred associated with nutritional and pathogen issues.

Results of analysis method. In accordance with the new regulation Regulation (EC) No 396/20051, European Food Safety Authority 2, 3 European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), Parma, Italy revised the MRLs and it is set that the new MRL of acetamidrid in pepper is 0.3 mg/kg.

Figure 3. Degradation curve for both doses and MRL

DISCUSSION

The validation parameters of acetamiprid determination GC-ECD were in accordance with the Environmental Protection Agency (Doc. No. 2010-2803) which also suggests the determination of acetamiprid residues by gas chromatography.

The maximum amount of acetamiprid residue is on the first day 0.774 mg/kg and the minimum is on the seventh day 0.029 mg/kg, which is the day of PHI (Pre Harvest Interval). It is noticed that acetamiprid degradation has a good performance on the date of PHI that is the seventh day of acetamiprid for vegetables, it results in values lower than 20 g dose MRL for a.i./ha.

The maximum amount of acetamiprid residue on the first day is 1.16 mg/kg and minimum in the seventh day is 0.19 mg/kg, which is the day PHI. It is noticed that degradation of acetamiprid has a good performance on the date of PHI that is the seventh day of acetamiprid for vegetables, it results in values lower than 30 g dose MRL for a.i./ha. Graph.2.

Lazić et al. (2008) did not detect the residues of this insecticide when analyzing 61 pepper samples for the content of 75 pesticides over the period 2005/2007, which indicates that by good agricultural practice the pesticide residues above the MRLs can be avoided, whereas, on the other hand, it can imply a rapid degradation of this insecticide (Khan, 2010 ili Roberts, 1998).

According to Roberts and Hutson (1999) when acetamiprid was applied as a granular formulation, parent insecticide and its metabolites were below the limit of detection (0.01 mg/kg). Thus our results also indicate that for both doses on the PHI have lower values of residues than the permitted level.

CONCLUSION

Acetamiprid is an appropriate insecticide to treat aphides in pepper cultivated greenhouses. Higher values than MRL are noticed until the fifth day respectively in 0.297 and 0.562 mg/kg. It is not recommended to harvest on the fifth day because it

poses a risk to consumers' health. Lower values than MRL of 0.029 and 0.19 mg/kg were noticed on the seventh day.

It is recommended to harvest after the seventh day on the treatment with acetamiprid. Individual pesticide residue methods are difficult, complicated, and costly methods which require highly skilled personnel and it is better to use the multiresidue method for pesticide analysis.

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HEMIJSKA KONTROLA VAŠI U ZAŠTIĆENOM PROSTORU I OSTACI ACETAMIPRIDA U PAPRICI

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Izvod

Predmet istraživanja su mere kontrole krompirove vaši (*Macrosiphum euphorbiae*, Thomas 1878) i metoda dredivanja ostataka insekticida acetamiprida, koji je korišćen za tretiranje paprike. Ovo ispitivanje je sprovedeno u plasteniku u okrugu Drač u 2011. godini. Eksperiment je zasnovan na upotrebi dve doze za tretiranje od 20 i 30 g a.s. acetamiprida / ha. Tretmani su izvedeni sa minimalnom i maksimalnom dozom primene. Utvrđeno je da je acetamiprid efikasan u suzbijanju vaši u paprikama. Uzorci su uzimani prvog, trećeg, petog i sedmog dana po tretiranju. Karenca za acetamiprid je sedam dana. Nakon isteka karence nivo ostataka acetamiprida je bio niži od maksimalno dozvoljenih količina (MDK). Naglašavamo da rezultati analize ukazuju da se mora poštovati propisani period karence, kako bi se izbegao povećan sadržaj ostataka acetamiprida u paprici.

Ključne reči: paprika, *Macrosiphum euphorbiae*, acetamiprid, ostaci, karenca, MDK.

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